

Efficiency vs. Complexity: Comparing Deep Learning and Machine Learning in High-Stakes Anomaly Detection

William Muntean, PhD; Zhuoran Wang, PhD; and Joseph Betts, PhD, EdS, MMIS

Remote Proctoring

- Provides testing convenience
- Augmented proctor security
- Exam interventions in real-time
- Greater flexibility in testing conditions

Research Goals

- Predict anomalous responses prior to item delivery
 - Compare gradient boosting with deep learning
- Predict shifts in responding strategies

Aberrant Responding

- Aberrant responding may occur for several reasons: cheating, careless responding, lucky guessing, creative responding, or random responding (Karabatsos, 2003)
- Global person-fit measures are often used to detect anomalous examinees
 - Conducted after exam completes
- Cumulative person-fit measures detect when a collective set of responses are anomalous
 - Neglect local anomalies

Strategy Shift

- Strategy shifts may occur for many reasons: time management, distractions, test anxiety, item harvesting, item pre-knowledge
- Not extensively researched
 - End of exam speediness

Pre-Classification

Detection Framework

Response Time Anomalies

- LightGBM has slightly stronger correlations with residual-only outliers than NBEATS
- Local Outlier Factor performs poorly

Item Response Anomalies

- LightGBM and NBEATS cannot make differentiated item-level IRT predictions
- This limits anomaly detection methods

Detecting Strategy Shifts

